

Targets and Ion Sources at CERN-ISOLDE - Facilities and Developments

S. Rothe^a, M. Au^{a,b}, J. Ballof^{a,b}, E. Barbero^a, M. Bissell^a, A. Boucherie^a, M. Bovigny^a, K. Chrysalidis^a, B. Crepieux^a, J. Cruikshank^a, E. Fadakis^a, R. Heinke^a, F. Josa^a, L. Le^a, A. Koliatos^a, E. Piselli^a, E. Reis^{a,c}, V. Samothrakis^a, M. Schütt^a, L. Lambert^a, D. Leimbach^{a,d}, S. Marzari^a, M. Owen^a, S. Stegemann^a, Y. N. Vila Gracia^a

^aCERN, Geneva, Switzerland

^bJohannes Gutenberg-Universität, Mainz, Germany

^cUniversität Duisburg-Essen, Duisburg, Germany

^dUniversity of Gothenburg, Gothenburg, Sweden

Abstract

At the CERN-ISOLDE radioactive ion beam facility, thick targets are irradiated using a beam of 1.4-GeV protons. One of ISOLDE's key features is the large choice of ion source types and target materials available, enabling us to select the ideal combination for optimal intensity and purity of the isotopes requested by ISOLDE users. The ever-increasing demands in terms of isotope production yield, beam purity, and overall reliability of the employed systems are driving the continuous development efforts.

Over the past few years, CERN has invested heavily in facilities and infrastructure that facilitate ongoing developments required for ISOLDE. A dedicated offline laboratory (Offline 2) has been recently equipped with high repetition rate nanosecond tunable lasers required for scheme development and developments of specialized laser ion source types such as VADLIS, LIST and PI-LIST. Moreover, it hosts a twin setup of the ISOLDE RFQ cooler and buncher (ISCOOL), which is envisaged to be used for studies of molecular beam creation and breakup, as well as the development of improved RFQ services and operational modes. For material development, particularly for nanostructured materials, the new nano laboratory has just been commissioned and will enable the production and development of nano actinide targets for ISOLDE. In this contribution we describe the infrastructure required for target and ion source developments, highlight recent efforts and experimental results on both target material development and ion source development, and provide an outlook on what to expect in the near future.

Keywords: ISOLDE, ion sources, radioactive ion beams, target materials

1. Introduction

ISOLDE is a radioactive ion beam (RIB) facility where over the last 50 years more than 1000 isotopes of 76 chemical elements have been produced [1–3]. The radioisotope inventory is created in a thick target through irradiation with a proton beam with an intensity of up to 2 μA and an energy of 1.4 GeV. The target material is positioned in a tubular tantalum oven (target container), which is heated restively to temperatures of typically 2000 °C which increases diffusion and effusion rates such that short-lived isotopes can reach the so-called transfer line and the ion source, where they are singly charged. A single-stage electrostatic extraction is used to form an ion beam with energies up to 60 keV. Isobars are selected using electric dipole magnets and this mass separated beam is then sent either to the low-energy beam lines or, after charge breeding, to the superconducting post accelerator and the HIE-ISOLDE [4, 5] experiments. ISOLDE users typically require highest intensity of a certain isotope. However, sensitivity to isobaric contamination is a common concern, and the target and ion source combination must therefore be carefully selected and adapted for each experiment. As a result, the target material and its microstructure must be deliberately chosen, to yield the highest nuclear cross section for the creation and the release of the desired isotope while still being chemically compatible to the respective

element. For example, reviews by Gottberg and Ramos [6, 7] explain the different target materials used at ISOL facilities in great detail. Most of the materials used at ISOLDE are carbides, followed by metals and oxides. Ionization sources exploited are the Resonance Ionization Laser Ion Source (RILIS, [8, 9]), surface ionization (positive and negative), and the (Forced Electron Beam Induced Arc Discharge) FEBIAD-type ion sources, requiring a calibrated leak for buffer gas injection, as pioneered by Kirchner [10] and adapted and optimized for use at ISOLDE [11, 12]. In addition, the ion sources can be connected to the target via a choice of transfer line types which allow further selection of the wanted chemical element through the variation of temperatures and/or materials [11, 13]. The ISOLDE target production follows the ISOLDE schedule [14] which requires about 30 target and ion source units to be produced per year, and, in order to ensure maximum yield and performance, new targets are typically used for the most demanding ion beams.

Throughout target operation, an observed decrease in yields of short-lived isotopes is attributed to sintering of the target material matrix which decreases the diffusion rate and therefore increases decay losses. Ion source failures, especially for the FEBIAD type sources, can lead to an abrupt end of an experimental campaign. The ISOLDE Target and Ion Source Development (TISD) teams are constantly improving all aspects of

the target and ion source system. This is a multidisciplinary endeavour which requires expertise in the fields of materials science, (thermo-)mechanical design, accelerator physics, chemistry as well as atomic and nuclear physics. We will illustrate the different facilities which are exploited for the developments and highlight examples of past and ongoing studies.

2. The offline mass separators

2.1. Offline 1

The offline 1 mass separator is an essential tool for target quality control, as well as target and ion source development. The initial concept was outlined in [15]. It is equipped with an ISOLDE target and ion source unit-compatible Frontend, along with all necessary services for operating the full range of ion sources required for ISOLDE online operation [16]. However, RILIS lasers were recently moved to a dedicated lab as part of Offline 2 (see section 2.2). The machine typically operates at ion beam energies of 30 keV. An Einzel lens is utilized for focusing of the beam emerging from the ion source and a detector chamber is situated in the separator magnet's focal point. The chamber contains adjustable slits, a Faraday cup and provisions for ion collection and single ion counting. An exit port on the beam axis can be used to attach auxiliary devices such as an emittance meter, collection or implantation chamber (see section 5.2).

Many development results were obtained in this laboratory, mainly addressing issues with beam contamination of laser-ionised species through use of low work-function hot cavity materials [17], and the Laser Ion source and Trap (LIST) [18, 19], along with work on beam purification using fast beam gating techniques [20]. Additionally, the VADLIS mode was developed by combining the FEBIAD ion source with RILIS [21], enabling the measurement of odd-even staggering in mercury at ISOLDE [22]. Revising the geometry improved the extraction of laser ions in the VADLIS 2.0 [23, 24].

Furthermore, negative surface ion sources have been investigated to deliver negative astatine (At) ions requested by ISOLDE users and additional work has been put into the negative ion beam development, e.g. through synthesising strontium vanadate low work function materials and their characterization in a dedicated electron emission setup shown in Fig. 1 [25]. Negative ions could also be extracted from a FEBIAD geometry with Cs injection. Further details are summarized in [26]. The KENIS [27] was refurbished and modified to use an external caesium reservoir instead of the commonly used dispenser, reducing the contaminants of oxygen and chromium in the ion beam.

Ion beam delivery of refractory elements such as boron (B) [28], molybdenum (Mo) [29] and selenium (Se) [30] has been studied using molecular ion beam formation. Offline 1 hosted a development program for molecular beams of refractory elements, during which samples of beryllium (Be) and silicon (Si) were extracted as molecular fluoride ion beams from the FEBIAD ion source. The production of molecular beams was optimized, and efficiencies of the ion sources were evaluated

before shipping for use at the batch-mode ion source (BMIS) [31] in a collaborative development with FRIB/MSU.

The facility is constantly evolving to meet the requirements for development campaigns while ensuring high reliability for the quality control of ISOLDE targets and ion sources. The LabVIEW-based control system has undergone a complete overhaul, as changes were made to ensure seamless integration with the existing CERN infrastructure, and new features were added as needed. For example, precise voltage supplies have been installed for the FEBIAD anode voltage control and drain current acquisition, which was crucial for investigations aimed at determining the relation between ionization potential (IP) of noble gasses and anode voltage. This method could be used to measure the IP of superheavy elements [29, 32, 33]. Furthermore, automatic correction of the mass separator field to account for anode voltage, automatic anode scan and Faraday cup recording tools were developed.

The gas injection system has been upgraded to use reactive gasses such as NF_3 , and the use of metallic seals and stainless steel piping has been enforced where possible. The bridge between the high voltage part and ground potential has been realized in PVDF to minimize permeation of oxygen and other contaminants into the setup. Beam instrumentation equipment such as Faraday cups and beam scanners can now be controlled by the respective Java based top level software also used at ISOLDE online.

2.2. Offline 2

The Offline 2 facility is a newly established offline mass separator facility designed to closely replicate the online ISOLDE systems.

It includes a radio-frequency quadrupole cooler and buncher (RFQcb), which is a replica of ISCOOL [34], and a dedicated RILIS laser laboratory equipped with a system of tunable titanium:sapphire (Ti:Sa) lasers, and high-power fixed-wavelength lasers. Laser beam access to the ion source coupled to the Frontend via a quartz window in the separator magnet enables RILIS developments for resonance ionization schemes and specialized ion sources including the LIST, VADLIS or the ToF-LIS, as well as investigations of the operational limits of the laser ion source.

The separator also provides a second laser entrance window, giving laser access to the RFQcb, which allows for the development of laser interaction techniques with trapped ions and molecules, such as breakup, optical pumping, and laser spectroscopy.

The Offline 2 facility was first commissioned [35, 36] before the CERN Long Shutdown 2 (LS2). It has been used to assemble and test the two new ISOLDE Frontends 10 and 11 before their installation online at the GPS and HRS, respectively. The original FE8 was reinstalled and upgraded to FE8+, making it now fully compatible to the latest FE design, and serving as spare for FEs 10 or 11. Two new gas systems have been designed and installed for the study of molecular beams formed in the ion source and in the RFQcb [37], and further upgrades of the facility are detailed in [38].

Offline 2 has been used to test and characterize the LIST source prior to irradiation at ISOLDE, especially in its novel Perpendicular Illumination (PI) mode for high-resolution applications [39]. The applicability of wavelength-range extension by Raman shifting of a standard Ti:Sa laser for RILIS operation was confirmed in this setup [40]. It has also been used to study laser effects on molecular beams [37], as well as the FEBIAD photocathode [41]. Recently, the facility was used to characterize the SPES surface ion source geometry [42] for the resonance laser ion source. Results of these tests will be published elsewhere.

2.3. Calibration Pumpstand

One part of the production process for target and ion sources involves vacuum testing and temperature calibration using an optical pyrometer. These tests are carried out at the Calibration Pumpstand, which is a high vacuum chamber equipped with all required service connectors to automatically couple a target unit and operate the target and the ion source. In addition, the pumpstand is also used for non-actinide target material production such as LaC carburization, conditioning of SiC pellets or zirconia fibers. Temperatures of more than 2100 °C can be obtained inside the tantalum oven. The setup was also used for the development and study of a boron nitride BN target material for the production of C-11 [43–45].

2.4. Ion source teststand

The RILIS laser activities have moved from Offline 1 to Offline 2, freeing up floor space for the new ion source teststand. Based on the design of the pumpstand, the teststand features an ISOLDE standard coupling table that enables the coupling of ISOLDE target and ion source units to a vacuum chamber and the necessary services for operating installed ion sources. While it has been recently used to further develop techniques for the ToF-LIS [20, 46, 47], it will be equipped with an ion extraction system [25] which will allow to measure the total ion current produced by the source under test. This will enable, for example, the measurement of integrated efficiencies across the lifetime of FEBIAD-type ion sources which are operated close to the limits of the materials. The 3D model, a photograph and the CST simulations are shown in Fig. 1.

3. Chemical laboratories

The chemical laboratories are primarily used for non-actinide target material production and development. There are four fume hoods and one inertable glove box available. Additionally, a suite of medium temperature ovens (1100 °C to 1500 °C) is available for heat treatment and chemical reactions under different atmospheres, such as argon, artificial air or high vacuum, which are controlled by a manual gas injection system and vacuum pumps. The high vacuum oven is used, for example, to produce the CaO nano material from CaCO₃ [48]. The same oven has been used to monitor partial pressures of CO and CO₂ during oxidation processes of LaC_x samples. For this purpose, an RGA operated at high vacuum was connected via a

Figure 1: Section view of the 3D model of the ion extraction and detection flange coupled to the ISOLDE target unit (top left), photograph of the assembled ion source teststand, showing the ion extraction flange and the residual gas analyser (bottom left), CST simulation of the ion trajectories, with the enabled deflector sending the ions to the Faraday cup for detection. (top right). Photograph of the ion extraction flange (bottom right). Figure from [25].

calibrated leak (1×10^{-4} mBar L s⁻¹) to the gas stream exiting the furnace [49].

Recently, a transfer shuttle (*CZF, ZEISS*) has been acquired to transport samples under inert atmosphere or vacuum between the glovebox and the SEM antechamber for the characterization of target materials using the scanning electron microscope (SEM, *FEG-SEM Sigma 500, ZEISS*) with an EDS X-Max Extreme Windowless 100 mm² detector (*Oxford Instrument*). This will be used for sensitive and/or hazardous materials. For example, CaO is chemically decomposed and loses its nano properties when exposed to air before it can be measured, LaC_x-nano is pyrophoric and nanofibre oxides are suspected to pose health risks.

In addition to the SEM, several other material characterization setups are present in the chemical labs, such as an adsorption-desorption isotherm device for specific surface area measurements, pore size and pore structure measurements (*Quantachrome 4000*), a helium pycnometer for density measurements (*Anton Paar Ultrapyc 5000*), and a particle size analyser (*Horiba LA-950*)

4. The nano actinide laboratory

The ISOLDE actinide target material production has to be carried out in a dedicated Class A laboratory. The conventional (micro-structured) UC_x and ThC_x materials were produced in fumehoods and with operators wearing personal pro-

protective equipment (respirators) wherever required to ensure safe handling. After mixing the two precursors: graphite (C) and uranium dioxide UO_2 in the required ratios, "green" pellets are produced using a rotary press. In a dedicated carburization pumpstand, the carbothermal reduction takes place under vacuum at $\approx 2 \times 10^{-4}$ mBar. An automated feedback and control system manages the heating current over the course of multiple days while maintaining the required low pressure and avoiding a runaway exothermic reaction. This system reduced the reaction time twofold with respect to fully manual operation, and pressure and current are recorded throughout the chemical reaction. Further reduction in reaction time has been demonstrated with increased operation pressure. [50, 51].

With the advent of nano actinide materials and the associated risks as well as for the general improvement of actinide handling, the building of the Class A laboratories has recently been extended to host the new actinide nano laboratory referred to as the Nanolab. This facility will be used to produce the standard micro-structured actinide targets as well as for the development and production of the new nano-structured actinide materials which have shown superior release properties [6, 48]. The layout of the Nanolab is shown in Fig. 2. The lab is partitioned into two main areas: the oxide lab and the carbide lab.

4.1. The oxide lab

The oxide lab is equipped with four interconnected glove boxes (GB1-GB4) which are operated in underpressure. The boxes can be flushed with compressed air, ensuring renewal of the atmosphere and mitigating any ATEX risks. In addition, heat sources are interlocked with solvent sensors. GB1 is used for weighing dry reactants (e.g. UO_2 and MWCNT). GB2 can be used for the production of the nanometric oxide precursor through grinding or other methods. GB3 houses the chemical reactor which can be used to mix the dispersion via sonication and/or stirring. A heating mantle and condenser are attached to contain and recycle the solvent. A membrane pump can be used for vacuum distillation and drying. GB4 houses the automatic 20 t hydraulic press *MIB PAC 20T*. A fumehood is available with storage space for solvents. Furthermore, there is space and services for an additional glovebox in the future. All gloveboxes have provisions for inertisation with argon gas.

4.2. The carbide lab

The centerpiece of the carbide lab is an inert glovebox (GB5) which works at underpressure. Oxygen and water levels are constantly monitored and a regeneration system keeps both below single-digit ppm. The main customization of this glovebox is the large antechamber which can be used to load an ISOLDE target unit into the glovebox. A ramp and trolley are used to move the target between the main chamber and antechamber. On both sides of the glove box, two pumpstands are available that can be used to couple the dedicated carburization target units. A transfer system has been developed to extract the carburized charge from the carburization oven into a transport vessel, which can then be coupled to GB5. Flushing and inertisation systems on both sides ensure that the carburized charge is

not exposed to air or moisture. In order to follow the paradigm of 'production to store', metallic storage capsules were developed which are used to store the different charges under inert atmosphere or under vacuum. A KF standard blind flange is used to close the capsule on one side while on the other side a miniature manometer indicates the inner pressure status. Capsules are used to store both un-carburized and carburized charges. Once all required target materials for the annual operation of ISOLDE have been produced and stored, the laboratory can be used for material development campaigns.

5. Ongoing developments and outlook

5.1. Target and ion source post-mortem analysis

The ISOLDE Hotcells have been used to disassemble the first irradiated targets (tantalum foil target material). While waste disposal is the primary purpose of disassembly, an important secondary goal is to take advantage of the unique opportunity for post-irradiation examination (PIE) to study certain failure modes of target materials, ion sources or vacuum vessels. This is standard procedure already in place at other facilities, such as TRIUMF-ISAC. For example, the examination of the internal proton-to-neutron converter (p2n) prototype target [52] will provide new directions for an improved thermal insulation concept.

Microtomography using the *ZEISS METROTOM 1500/225 kV* has been employed for the post-mortem analysis of a non-irradiated FEBIAD ion source. Figure 3 shows a cross-sectional view of the cathode region of the ion source, where the deformation of the face of the cathode and the resulting misalignment are clearly visible. This non-destructive step can be performed before further disassembly of the source, during which some parts inevitably become distorted or break due to embrittlement after operation at high temperatures.

5.2. Ion implantation setup

The use of residual gas analysers (RGA) on vacuum installations has proven valuable for various applications related to target material and ion source development. They were used during the development phase of new gas injection systems, during the operation of plasma ion sources to monitor (reactive) gas injection, as well as to detect origins of vacuum issues due to outgassing or to follow the chemical reactions during material thermal treatment [49]. Currently, an ion implantation setup is being commissioned which is intended to be used for molecular beam development and initial diffusion studies for new target materials. In this setup, ions with an energy of 30 keV from Offline 1 are implanted into a substrate for a certain amount of time, after which the vacuum chamber is isolated from the mass separator and the substrate is heated. The volatilized species are then detected using an RGA located close to the sample region. The molecular breakup patterns in the RGA mass spectrum can then reveal the composition of the implanted molecule. Systematic temperature and time-resolved data can be used to infer relative diffusion properties of sample materials.

Figure 2: Layout of the ISOLDE Nano Lab.

Figure 3: Image obtained from microtomography scan of a faulty FEBIAD ion source

5.3. Non-actinide nano material development

An electrospinning setup (*Ske Systems EF 100*) has been purchased, and used for the first commissioning tests with zirconium solutions. The goal is to develop processes resulting in nanofibre carbides and oxides which are produced after the debinding step where the added polymers are evaporated in reducing or oxidizing atmosphere. The glovebox in the chemical lab has been adapted to operate a dedicated debinding oven, which can be flushed with argon and air, but allows safe handling of nanofibers after the debinding process. A similar system has been used for the production of silicon carbide fibres [53].

Methods to obtain nanometric precursors alternative to the grinding process using a ball mill (currently employed for the nano UO_x and LaC_x) are also investigated, which include low- and high-pressure decomposition of oxalates and carbonates.

Freeze-cast yttria samples with tailored nano-pores [54], produced in collaboration with the University of Duisburg-Essen, have been heat treated and tested for thermal and morphological stability.

5.4. Molecular beams

The beam development for fundamental physics using radioactive molecules [55] has been triggered by the first laser spectroscopy performed on radioactive radium fluoride (RaF) molecules [56]. A dedicated target and ion source unit was built which holds an externally heated reaction chamber with reactive gas injection, coupled to a FEBIAD ion source [57]. This setup was used for initial studies for alternative delivery of fluorine as a reactant via decomposition of composites rather than injection of reactive gasses such as SF_6 , CF_4 or NF_3 .

5.5. Target container optimization

Target container thermal optimization studies are typically performed at the pumpstand. A special target lid with four additional viewports is used to gain access to measure temperatures using pyrometers to validate the thermomechanical design. Current developments aim for homogenization of target container and transferline/ion-source heating, thus reducing cold spots and therefore potential loss of short-lived isotopes.

A prototype design as shown in Fig. 4 has been successfully operated at ISOLDE for the production of nickel beams, which has been challenging due to adsorption of nickel on tantalum surfaces [58] resulting in long retention times and therefore loss of short-lived species. The prototype utilized the new back-of-the-transferline heating and additional features of the target container, including reduction of the thickness of the target leads to 2 mm and reduction of the thermal mass of the endcaps. Furthermore, tungsten foil was used to line the target and transfer line, to avoid contact between nickel isotopes and tantalum surfaces. While standard metallic heat screens were used during the irradiation of this prototype target at ISOLDE, porous carbon-based alternative heat screens (e.g. Sigratherm MFA), which were already used in the internal proton to neutron converter concept [52], have been tested to allow for heating the 40 mm diameter container to the required temperatures. Currently, a modular heat screen configuration based on MFA

Figure 4: (a) The 3D model of the new container with reduced wall thickness and target leads. (b) A cross section view of the target ion source.

plates is being tested for the standard diameter container (20 mm), which shows promising performance in terms of long-term temperature stability and homogeneity.

5.6. Additive manufacturing

Selective Laser Melting is a powerful technique to create shapes of metallic objects that are not available through conventional machining. Such 3D printed parts have been used at ISOLDE and at CERN for beam instrumentation [59] and other domains for accelerator technology [60] for example niobium superconducting cavities [61].

Parts in standard geometry for the FEBIAD ion source (anode body and cathode), the MK1 surface ion source as well as the MK4 negative surface ion source (LaB₆ pellet holder) have been printed in niobium. In order to quantify outgassing behaviour, the niobium anode was placed inside an ISOLDE target oven coupled to a FEBIAD ion source and the absence of strong contamination was confirmed via a mass spectroscopy at Offline 1.

Rebesan et al. [62] have investigated molybdenum printing, and were able to manufacture an anode body. This molybdenum anode has been installed in a standard SPES FEBIAD ion source and was successfully tested and characterized at the Offline 1 facility. The results will be published in a forthcoming article.

At the moment, the AMIS project (Applications of refractory Metals for Ion Source cavities), funded by the iFAST innovation fund [63], aims at optimizing the FEBIAD ion source, exploiting the full AM potential. INFN-SPES, CERN-ISOLDE and TRIUMF-ISAC/ARIEL are collaborating for ion source modelling, thermomechanical simulation and final testing of the concepts.

Acknowledgments

This project has received funding from the European's Union Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement number 861198 project 'LISA' (Laser Ionization and

Spectroscopy of Actinides) Marie Skłodowska-Curie Innovative Training Network (ITN). The SY-Small projects initiative has funded the Wien filter, the electrospinning setup and the dedicated tantalum additive manufacturing platform. We thank the EN-MME teams for performing the micro tomography, the SEM imaging and for the collaboration on the additive manufacturing work.

References

- [1] E. Kugler, D. Fiander, B. Johnson, H. Haas, A. Przewłoka, H. L. Ravn, et al. "The new CERN-ISOLDE on-line mass-separator facility at the PS-Booster". In: *Nucl. Instrum. Methods B* 70.1-4 (Aug. 1992), pp. 41–49. doi: 10.1016/0168-583X(92)95907-9.
- [2] R. Catherall, W. Andrezza, M. Breitenfeldt, A. Dorsival, G. J. Focker, T. P. Gharsa, et al. "The ISOLDE facility". In: *Journal of Physics G: Nuclear and Particle Physics* 44.9 (Sept. 2017), p. 094002. doi: 10.1088/1361-6471/aa7eba.
- [3] J. Ballof, J. Ramos, A. Molander, K. Johnston, S. Rothe, T. Stora, et al. "The upgraded ISOLDE yield database – A new tool to predict beam intensities". In: *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms* 463 (Jan. 2020), pp. 211–215. doi: 10.1016/j.nimb.2019.05.044.
- [4] M. Lindroos and CERN. "HIE-ISOLDE : the technical options". In: (2006). doi: 10.5170/CERN-2006-013.
- [5] R. Catherall, M. Augustin, C. Babcock, R. Barlow, A. Bernardes, S. Cimmino, et al. "An overview of the HIE-ISOLDE Design Study". In: *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms* 317.PART B (Dec. 2013), pp. 204–207. doi: 10.1016/j.nimb.2013.07.030.
- [6] A. Gottberg. "Target materials for exotic ISOL beams". In: *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms* 376 (June 2016), pp. 8–15. doi: 10.1016/j.nimb.2016.01.020.
- [7] J. P. Ramos. "Thick solid targets for the production and online release of radioisotopes: The importance of the material characteristics – A review". In: *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research, Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms* 463 (Jan. 2020), pp. 201–210. doi: 10.1016/j.nimb.2019.05.045.
- [8] V. Fedosseev, K. Chrysalidis, T. D. Goodacre, B. Marsh, S. Rothe, C. Seiffert, et al. "Ion beam production and study of radioactive isotopes with the laser ion source at ISOLDE". In: *Journal of Physics G: Nuclear and Particle Physics* 44.8 (Aug. 2017), p. 084006. doi: 10.1088/1361-6471/aa78e0.

- [9] V. Mishin, V. Fedoseyev, H.-J. Kluge, V. Letokhov, H. Ravn, F. Scheerer, et al. “Chemically selective laser ion-source for the CERN-ISOLDE on-line mass separator facility”. In: *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms* 73.4 (Apr. 1993), pp. 550–560. doi: 10.1016/0168-583X(93)95839-W.
- [10] R. Kirchner and E. Roeckl. “Investigation of gaseous discharge ion sources for isotope separation on-line”. In: *Nuclear Instruments and Methods* 133.2 (Mar. 1976), pp. 187–204. doi: 10.1016/0029-554X(76)90607-8.
- [11] S. Sundell and H. Ravn. “Ion source with combined cathode and transfer line heating”. In: *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms* 70.1-4 (Aug. 1992), pp. 160–164. doi: 10.1016/0168-583X(92)95926-I.
- [12] L. Penescu, R. Catherall, J. Lettry, and T. Stora. “Development of high efficiency Versatile Arc Discharge Ion Source at CERN ISOLDE”. In: *Review of Scientific Instruments* 81.2 (Feb. 2010), 02A906. doi: 10.1063/1.3271245.
- [13] E. Bouquerel, R. Catherall, M. Eller, J. Lettry, S. Marzari, and T. Stora. “Beam purification by selective trapping in the transfer line of an ISOL target unit”. In: *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research, Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms* 266.19-20 (Oct. 2008), pp. 4298–4302. doi: 10.1016/j.nimb.2008.05.060.
- [14] K. Johnston. *ISOLDE Schedule — ISOLDE*. 2022.
- [15] J. Lettry. *Off-Line Isotope Separator*. Tech. rep. Mar. 1994. doi: 10.17181/CERN.74PM.BVI3.
- [16] R. Kirchner. “Ion sources for radioactive beams and related problems (Review) (invited)”. In: *Review of Scientific Instruments* 67.3 (June 1998), p. 928. doi: 10.1063/1.1146774.
- [17] F. Schwellnus, R. Catherall, B. Crepieux, V. Fedosseev, B. Marsh, C. Mattolat, et al. “Study of low work function materials for hot cavity resonance ionization laser ion sources”. In: *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms* 267.10 (May 2009), pp. 1856–1861. doi: 10.1016/j.nimb.2009.02.068.
- [18] F. Schwellnus, K. Blaum, R. Catherall, B. Crepieux, V. Fedosseev, T. Gottwald, et al. “The laser ion source trap for highest isobaric selectivity in online exotic isotope production”. In: *Review of Scientific Instruments* 81.2 (Feb. 2010), 02A515. doi: 10.1063/1.3318259.
- [19] D. Fink, S. Richter, B. Bastin, K. Blaum, R. Catherall, T. Cocolios, et al. “First application of the Laser Ion Source and Trap (LIST) for on-line experiments at ISOLDE”. In: *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms* 317.PART B (Dec. 2013), pp. 417–421. doi: 10.1016/j.nimb.2013.06.039.
- [20] S. Rothe, R. Catherall, B. Crepieux, T. Day Goodacre, V. N. Fedosseev, T. Giles, et al. “Advances in surface ion suppression from RILIS: Towards the Time-of-Flight Laser Ion Source (ToF-LIS)”. In: *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research, Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms* 376 (June 2016), pp. 86–90. doi: 10.1016/j.nimb.2016.02.060.
- [21] T. Day Goodacre, J. Billowes, R. Catherall, T. Cocolios, B. Crepieux, D. Fedorov, et al. “Blurring the boundaries between ion sources: The application of the RILIS inside a FEBIAD type ion source at ISOLDE”. In: *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms* 376 (June 2016), pp. 39–45. doi: 10.1016/j.nimb.2016.03.005.
- [22] B. A. Marsh, T. Day Goodacre, S. Sels, Y. Tsunoda, B. Andel, A. N. Andreyev, et al. “Characterization of the shape-staggering effect in mercury nuclei”. In: *Nature Physics* 14.12 (Dec. 2018), pp. 1163–1167. doi: 10.1038/s41567-018-0292-8.
- [23] Y. Martinez Palenzuela, B. Marsh, J. Ballof, R. Catherall, K. Chrysalidis, T. Cocolios, et al. “Enhancing the extraction of laser-ionized beams from an arc discharge ion source volume”. In: *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms* 431 (Sept. 2018), pp. 59–66. doi: 10.1016/j.nimb.2018.06.006.
- [24] Y. Martinez Palenzuela. “Characterization and optimization of a versatile laser and electron-impact ion source for radioactive ion beam production at ISOLDE and MEDICIS”. PhD thesis. Apr. 2019.
- [25] D. Leimbach. “Negative Ion Source Development and Photodetachment Studies at ISOLDE”. PhD thesis. Gothenburg university, 2017. doi: 10.17181/CERN-THESIS-2017-337.
- [26] D. Leimbach. “Radioactive negative ions: Production and laser spectroscopy at ISOLDE”. PhD thesis. 2021, p. 244. doi: 10.17181/CERN-THESIS-2021-083.
- [27] G. D. Alton, Y. Liu, C. Williams, and S. N. Murray. “A high efficiency, kinetic-ejection negative ion source for RIB generation”. In: *AIP Conference Proceedings* 473.1 (Apr. 2008), p. 330. doi: 10.1063/1.58953.
- [28] J. Ballof, C. Seiffert, B. Crepieux, C. E. C. E. Düllmann, M. Delonca, M. Gai, et al. “Radioactive boron beams produced by isotope online mass separation at CERN-ISOLDE”. In: 55.5 (May 2019), p. 65. doi: 10.1140/epja/i2019-12719-1.
- [29] J. Ballof and G. In Wiesbaden. *Radioactive Molecular Beams at CERN-ISOLDE*. 2021.
- [30] K. Chrysalidis, J. Ballof, C. Düllmann, V. Fedosseev, C. Granados, B. Marsh, et al. “Developments towards the delivery of selenium ion beams at ISOLDE”. In: *European Physical Journal A* 55.10 (2019). doi: 10.1140/epja/i2019-12873-4.
- [31] Chandana Sumithrarachchi and others. “The new Batch Mode Ion Source (BMIS) for stand-alone operation of the ReA reaccelerator at the Facility for Rare Isotope Beams (FRIB)”. In: *EMIS 2022 at RAON*. 2023.
- [32] J. Ballof, T. Stora, C. E. Düllmann, D. Leimbach, A. Ringvall-Molberg, S. Rothe, et al. *Ion sources for superheavy elements: Towards ionisation potential (IP) measurements with the VADIS source*. Feb. 2019. doi: 10.5281/ZENODO.7646730.
- [33] David Leimbach. *Target and ion source developments*. 2019.
- [34] I. Podadera Aliseda. “New developments on preparation of cooled and bunched radioactive ion beams at ISOL-Facilities: the ISCOOL project and the rotating wall cooling”. PhD thesis. Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya, 2006.
- [35] S. Warren, T. Giles, C. Pequeno, and A. Ringvall-Moberg. “Offline 2, ISOLDE’s target, laser and beams development facility”. In: *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms* 463 (Jan. 2020), pp. 115–118. doi: 10.1016/j.nimb.2019.07.016.
- [36] A. R. Moberg, S. Warren, M. L. Bissell, B. Crepieux, T. Giles, D. Leimbach, et al. “The Offline 2 facility at ISOLDE, CERN”. In: (Nov. 2022). doi: 10.17181/CERN-OPEN-2022-015.
- [37] M. Au. “Laser effects on Molecules”. In: *EMIS 2022 Proceedings* (2023).
- [38] M. Schütt. “No Title”. In: *EMIS 2022 Proceedings* (2023).
- [39] R. Heinke. *Prospects for high resolution in-source spectroscopy using cross laser / atom beam geometry: Nuclear structure investigation on actinium isotopes with ISOLDE’s new ion source PI-LIST · IBS Indico System*.
- [40] D. T. Echarrri, K. Chrysalidis, V. N. Fedosseev, R. Heinke, B. A. Marsh, B. B. Reich, et al. “Tunable diamond raman lasers for resonance photo-ionization and ion beam production”. In: *Frontiers in Physics* 10 (July 2022), p. 697. doi: 10.3389/fphy.2022.937976/BIBTEX.
- [41] J. Ballof, M. Au, E. Barbero, K. Chrysalidis, C. E. Düllmann, V. Fedosseev, et al. “A cold electron-impact ion source driven by a photocathode – New opportunities for the delivery of radioactive molecular beams?” In: *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* 2244.1 (Apr. 2022), p. 012072. doi: 10.1088/1742-6596/2244/1/012072.
- [42] M. Manziolaro, F. D’Agostini, A. Monetti, and A. Andrighetto. “The SPES surface ionization source”. In: *Review of Scientific Instruments* 88.9 (Sept. 2017), p. 093302. doi: 10.1063/1.4998246.

- [43] S. Stegemann, T. E. Cocolios, K. Dockx, G. Leinders, L. Popescu, J. P. Ramos, et al. “Production of intense mass separated 11C beams for PET-aided hadron therapy”. In: *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms* 463 (Jan. 2020), pp. 403–407. doi: 10.1016/J.NIMB.2019.04.042.
- [44] S. Stegemann, J. Ballof, T. E. Cocolios, J. G. Correia, K. Dockx, O. Poleshchuk, et al. “A porous hexagonal boron nitride powder compact for the production and release of radioactive 11C”. In: *Journal of the European Ceramic Society* 41.7 (July 2021), pp. 4086–4097. doi: 10.1016/J.JEURCERAMSOC.2020.12.029.
- [45] S. Stegemann. “Production of mass separated ^{11}C beams for PET-aided hadron therapy”. PhD thesis. KU Leuven, 2022.
- [46] J. Lettry, R. Catherall, U. Köster, U. Georg, O. Jonsson, S. Marzari, et al. “Alkali suppression within laser ion-source cavities and time structure of the laser ionized ion-bunches”. In: *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms* 204 (May 2003), pp. 363–367. doi: 10.1016/S0168-583X(02)01967-5.
- [47] R. Heinke, M. Barnes, K. Chrysalidis, L. Ducimetiere, V. Fedosseev, I. Hendriks, et al. “Modulated RILIS heating - small project proposal”. In: (Feb. 2023). doi: 10.5281/ZENODO.7642660.
- [48] J. Ramos, A. Gottberg, R. Augusto, T. Mendonca, K. Riisager, C. Seifert, et al. “Target nanomaterials at CERN-ISOLDE: synthesis and release data”. In: *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms* 376 (June 2016), pp. 81–85. doi: 10.1016/j.nimb.2016.03.003.
- [49] L. Coulaud and S. De Man. *Oxidation of lanthanum carbide and graphite targets*. Tech. rep. June 2022. doi: 10.17181/CERN-OPEN-2023-002.
- [50] J. Guillot. “Development of radioactive beams : Influence of the UCx Target Microstructure on the Release Properties of Fission Products”. In: (Sept. 2017).
- [51] M. Cervantes, P. Fouquet-Métivier, P. Kunz, L. Lambert, A. Mjos, T. Day Goodacre, et al. “UCx target production at TRIUMF in the ARIEL era”. In: *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms* 463 (Jan. 2020), pp. 367–370. doi: 10.1016/J.NIMB.2019.04.058.
- [52] J. Ramos, M. Ballan, L. Egoriti, D. Hougbo, S. Rothe, R. Augusto, et al. “Design and tests for the new CERN-ISOLDE spallation source: an integrated tungsten converter surrounded by an annular UC target operated at 2000 °C”. In: *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms* 463 (Jan. 2020), pp. 357–363. doi: 10.1016/j.nimb.2019.04.060.
- [53] J. Wong. “Development of nanofibrous target materials for short-lived isotope production”. In: (2018). doi: 10.14288/1.0371625.
- [54] E. Kröll, M. Vadalà, J. Schell, S. Stegemann, J. Ballof, S. Rothe, et al. “Yttrium oxide freeze-casts: Target materials for radioactive ion beams”. In: *Materials* 14.11 (May 2021), p. 2864. doi: 10.3390/ma14112864.
- [55] G. Arrowsmith-Kron, M. Athanasakis-Kaklamanakis, M. Au, J. Ballof, R. Berger, A. Borschevsky, et al. “Opportunities for Fundamental Physics Research with Radioactive Molecules”. In: (Feb. 2023). doi: 10.48550/arxiv.2302.02165.
- [56] R. F. Garcia Ruiz, R. Berger, J. Billowes, C. L. Binnersley, M. L. Bissell, A. A. Breier, et al. “Spectroscopy of short-lived radioactive molecules”. In: *Nature* 2020 581:7809 581.7809 (May 2020), pp. 396–400. doi: 10.1038/s41586-020-2299-4.
- [57] VASILEIOS SAMOTHRAKIS. *MEDICIS & ISOLDE Target Report 2*. Tech. rep.
- [58] U. Köster. “Yields and spectroscopy of radioactive isotopes at LOHENGRIN and ISOLDE”. PhD thesis. 1999, p. 300.
- [59] R. Veness, W. Andrezza, D. Gudkov, A. M. Marin, S. Samuelsson, and G. Switzerland. “Metal 3D Additive Machining for in-Vacuum Beam Instrumentation”. In: (2018), TUPH36. doi: 10.18429/JACOW-MEDSI2018-TUPH36.
- [60] N. Delerue, A. Simar, R. L. Gerard, H. Carduner, S. Jenzer, P. Manil, et al. “JACoW : Prospects of additive manufacturing for accelerators”. In: (2019), THPTS008. doi: 10.18429/JACOW-IPAC2019-THPTS008.
- [61] F. Motschmann, R. Gerard, and F. Gilles. “Purification of Selective Laser Melting Additive Manufactured Niobium for Superconducting RF-Applications Transactions on Applied Superconductivity”. In: *IEEE Transactions on Applied Superconductivity* 29.5 (Aug. 2019). doi: 10.1109/TASC.2019.2900521.
- [62] P. Rebesan, M. Ballan, M. Bonesso, A. Campagnolo, S. Corradetti, R. Dima, et al. “Pure molybdenum manufactured by Laser Powder Bed Fusion: Thermal and mechanical characterization at room and high temperature”. In: *Additive Manufacturing* 47 (Nov. 2021), p. 102277. doi: 10.1016/J.ADDMA.2021.102277.
- [63] iFAST. *I.FAST Innovation Fund — IFAST*. 2023.